

Invisible Beneficial Microorganisms: The Underground Workforce Enhancing and Protecting Our Crops

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Abstract

Beneath the soil surface exists a highly active and diverse microbial ecosystem that plays a fundamental role in sustaining agriculture and global food production. Among these microorganisms, plant growth promoting microorganisms (PGPMs), including beneficial bacteria and fungi, establish close associations with plant roots and significantly influence plant performance. They enhance nutrient acquisition by fixing atmospheric nitrogen, solubilizing phosphorus and other essential minerals, and improving nutrient mobilization in the rhizosphere. Many PGPMs also synthesize phytohormones that stimulate root and shoot development, thereby improving water and nutrient uptake efficiency. In addition, they protect plants from pathogens through competition, antibiosis, enzyme production, and activation of plant defense responses. With increasing challenges such as climate change, soil degradation, emerging diseases, and rising food demand, sustainable agricultural strategies are urgently needed. PGPMs offer an eco-friendly and cost-effective alternative to excessive chemical inputs. By improving soil health, enhancing stress tolerance, and supporting consistent crop productivity, these beneficial microbes contribute to resilient farming systems. Harnessing this hidden microbial potential can help to shape a more sustainable and productive future for global agriculture. Integrating PGPM-based approaches into mainstream farming practices can reduce reliance on synthetic fertilizers and pesticides while maintaining soil health and ecological balance.

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Introduction

Agriculture is vital for sustaining the growing global population, yet crop productivity is increasingly challenged by biotic and abiotic stresses such as climate variability, pathogens, abiotic stresses and declining arable land (Junaid and Gokce, 2024). Although chemical fertilizers enhance yield, their excessive and prolonged use degrades soil health, disrupts microbial balance, and threatens long-term sustainability (Zambrano-Mendoza et al., 2021). Soil is a dynamic ecosystem that harbors diverse microbial communities, including plant growth promoting microorganisms (PGPMs), which regulate nutrient cycling and support soil structure (Chauhan et al., 2023). Through close

interactions with plant roots, these beneficial microbes enhance nutrient availability, stimulate growth, and improve plant resilience against stresses (Figure1), highlighting their importance in sustainable agriculture (Singh et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2024).

Fig.1: Different mechanisms employed by plant growth promoting microorganism to enhance plant growth and health.

Rhizosphere- PGPM Interactions

The rhizosphere is the narrow soil zone influenced by plant roots and serves as an active site for

Table 1: Beneficial microorganisms and their associated crops highlighting key functions in plant growth promotion and protection.

S.No.	Microorganisms	Plant / Crop	Key Functions in Plant Growth and Protection	References
2.	Bacillus and Paenibacillus sp.	Maize	Combat of Zn and Fe malnutrition in maize.	Ahmad et al., 2024
3.	Pseudomonas palleroniana N26 and Pseudomonas jessenii MP1	Kidney bean	Enhanced nutrient mobilization, increasing grain yield, protein, and zinc content	Khan et al., 2023
4.	B. ottawaense SG09 and Pseudomonas species	Soybean	Improved biomass and grain yield.	Win et al., 2024
5.	Pseudomonas protegens	Wheat	Enhanced zinc biofortification under saline stress conditions.	Singh et al., 2022

Direct Mechanisms in Plant Growth Enhancement and Protection

Rhizosphere microorganisms enhance plant growth through direct mechanisms that improve nutrient acquisition and regulate plant physiology. These beneficial effects are primarily achieved through the following mechanisms:

Nitrogen fixation

Certain rhizobacteria convert atmospheric nitrogen (N₂) into plant-assimilable forms such as ammonia (NH₃), improving nitrogen availability in nutrient-deficient soils (Pérez-Montaña et al., 2025);

Phosphorus solubilization

Phosphate-solubilizing bacteria and mycorrhizal fungi enhance phosphorus bioavailability by solubilizing inorganic phosphates and mineralizing organic forms (Timofeeva et al., 2023);

Siderophore production

PGPM produce siderophores that chelate iron, increasing its availability to plants and supporting growth (Timofeeva et al., 2023);

Auxin (IAA) production

Many PGPM synthesize indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), which stimulates root and shoot development, cell elongation, vascular differentiation, and improved root colonization (Orozco-Mosqueda et al., 2023).

Indirect Mechanisms in Plant Growth Enhancement and Protection

Plant growth-promoting microorganisms (PGPMs) enhance plant health indirectly through

nutrient exchange and microbial activity. It harbors diverse microorganisms that drive key biogeochemical processes thereby supporting soil fertility and plant productivity (Larsen et al., 2015). Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) are beneficial inhabitants of this region that enhance plant performance through multiple mechanisms (Table 1).

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biological control and stress mitigation strategies that suppress pathogens and strengthen plant defense systems: *Competition for nutrients and space:*

Biocontrol agents compete with pathogens for limited resources such as carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, and ecological niches. Effective suppression occurs when the antagonist colonizes the rhizosphere efficiently and utilizes resources more effectively than the pathogen (Jamalizadeh et al., 2011);

Antibiosis:

Certain microorganisms produce antibiotics, toxins, and other inhibitory metabolites that suppress or destroy pathogens. These compounds may be synthesized under varying nutrient conditions and function at low concentrations (Jamalizadeh et al., 2011);

Induced systemic resistance (ISR):

PGPM can trigger plant defense pathways, activating defense-related enzymes and proteins that enhance resistance against pathogens and insect pests (Meena et al., 2020);

Abiotic stress tolerance:

PGPM improve plant resilience to drought, salinity, heat, and heavy metal stress by modulating phytohormone levels, producing ACC deaminase, siderophores, volatile organic compounds, and protective enzymes (Bhat et al., 2022).

Conclusion

In conclusion, plant growth promoting microorganisms are an essential yet often under recognized component of agricultural systems. By

naturally improving nutrient availability, suppressing plant diseases, and enhancing tolerance to environmental stresses, these beneficial microbes provide a sustainable approach to crop production. Their adoption in farming practices can decrease reliance on synthetic inputs while supporting long-term soil health and food security. The foundation of resilient agriculture may, therefore, depend on the microbial life present in the soil.

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